

Fast-Track Your Knowledge of the Student Organiser Project – get up to speed in 6 hours or less

Brief introduction – 5 minutes then ask questions

The Student Organiser is an open-source web application used by WEHI RCP to streamline the recruitment, onboarding, and management of student interns.

- **Scale:** Handles ~100-150 student applications per intake, 3 intakes per year

The student organiser uses:

- Python: Core programming language for backend logic
- Flask: Web framework for routing and request handling
- SQLite3: Database for storing student data
- HTML/CSS/JavaScript: Frontend application logic
- GitHub: Version control

High-Level Workflows the system follows – 5 minutes then ask questions

- Monitor
- Submissions
 - Attendance
 - Participation

Understanding Project Architecture - 35 minutes then ask questions

Project structure – 5 minutes then ask questions

```

student-intern-organiser/
├── app.py # Main Flask application
├── schema.sql # Database table definitions
├── import_csv_from_redcap.py # REDCap data import
├── templates/ # HTML templates
│   ├── base.html # Base template layout
│   ├── index.html # Homepage
│   └── [other views].html # Various pages
├── static/ # Static assets
│   ├── css/ # Stylesheets
│   └── js/ # JavaScript files
├── sql_upgrades/ # Database migrations
├── demo/ # Demo/test files
└── .venv/ # Virtual environment

student_intern_data/ # Data repository
├── setup_database.py # Database initialization
├── create_dummy_data.py # Test data generator
├── upload_csv.py # CSV import utility
├── student_intern_data.db # SQLite database
├── test_students.csv # Sample data
├── statuses.tsv # Status definitions
├── import_students_from_redcap/ # REDCap integration
└── attachments/ # Document storage
  
```

Web application architecture – 30 minutes then ask questions

Students index page

1. WEHI logo links back to menu function page
2. page address after 'http://127.0.0.1:5000'; determined in function in app.py (Page 2)
3. page header base.html

Page 1

127.0.0.1:5000

WEHI All Students
brighter together

All Students Index Dashboard Download contracts Current Intake New Intake WIP New Intake All Share Student Applications Import REDCap Intakes Projects Links

Copy Personal Emails Copy WEHI Emails Download Key Attributes 01 Received application Change Status Genomics Metadata Multiplexing Change Project

N/A Change Rating N/A Change Course N/A Change pronouns N/A Change phone

Showing 1 to 50 of 62 entries Search:

<input type="checkbox"/>	ID	Name	Pronunciation	Pronouns	University Email	Key Skill	Mobile	Project	Intake	Course	Status	Pre Internship Summary	Post Internship Rating	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	101	Anika Sharma	None	he/him	owen@example.com	N/A	2109876543	Genomics Metadata Multiplexing	1 - Semester 2 2021	Science	14 Finished	4 F Technical Skills - Recommend sign up for a specific project.	N/A	View Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	102	Igor Petrov	None	he/him	owen@example.com	N/A	2109876543	Data Commons	1 - Semester 2 2021	Science	14 Finished		N/A	View Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	103	Pavel Ivanov	None	he/him	owen@example.com	N/A	2109876543	Data Commons	1 - Semester 2 2021	Science	14 Finished		N/A	View Edit
<input type="checkbox"/>	104	Hassan Al-Rashid	None	he/him	owen@example.com	N/A	2109876543	Data Commons	1 - Semester 2 2021	Science	14 Finished		N/A	View Edit

Page 2

```
app.py > index_current
1736 @app.route('/') → 4
1737 def index():
1738     # Connect to the SQLite database
1739     conn = sqlite3.connect(db_path)
1740     cursor = conn.cursor()
1741
1742     # Retrieve student data from the database
1743     cursor.execute("""
1744         SELECT
1745             s.intern_id,
1746             s.full_name,
1747             s.email,
1748             s.pronunciation,
1749             p.name AS project,
1750             i.name AS intake,
1751             s.course,
1752             st.name AS status,
1753             s.post_internship_summary_rating_internal,
1754             s.pronouns,
1755             CAST(COALESCE(s.pre_internship_internal_eval_level_id, '') AS TEXT) || ' ' || COALESCE(lvl.name, ''),
1756             s.show_key_skill,
1757             s.mobile
1758         FROM Students s
1759         LEFT JOIN Projects p ON s.project_id = p.id
1760         LEFT JOIN Intakes i ON s.intake_id = i.id
1761         LEFT JOIN Statuses st ON s.status_id = st.id
1762         LEFT JOIN internal_eval_levels lvl ON s.pre_internship_internal_eval_level_id = lvl.id
1763     """)
1764     students = cursor.fetchall() → 6
1765
1766     cursor.execute('SELECT * FROM Projects')
1767     projects = cursor.fetchall()
1768
1769     # Retrieve student data from the database
1770     cursor.execute('SELECT * FROM Statuses')
1771     statuses = cursor.fetchall()
1772
1773     # Close the database connection
1774     conn.close()
1775     title_of_page = "All Students" → 7
1776     return render_template('index.html', students=students, statuses=statuses, title_of_page=title_of_page, projects=projects)
```

4. page address; shown after 'http://127.0.0.1:5000' in webpage (Page 1)

5. queries fields from students database

6. retrieve all students which satisfy the given condition(s) and store in variable 'students' as a list

7. index.html file (Page 3) is the webpage template to be displayed with the selected students, statuses, projects data

Page 3

```
templates > <> index.html
75 {% block content %}
76 <table id="studentTable"> → 8
77 <tbody>
78     {% for student in students %}
79     <tr>
80         <td><input type="checkbox" class="studentCheckbox"></td> <!-- Checkbox column -->
81         <td><a href="/pre_int_st_evaluation/{{ student[0] }}">{{ student[0] }}</a></td>
82         <td>{{ student[1] }}</td>
83         <td>{{ student[3] }}</td>
84         <td>{{ student[9] }}</td>
85         {% if student[2] and student[2] != '' %}
86         <td><a href="mailto:{{ student[2] }}">{{ student[2] }}</a></td>
87         {% else %}
88         <td></td>
89         {% endif %}
90     </tr>
91     {% endfor %}
92 </tbody>
93 </table>
94 </block content %>
```

8. students data retrieved in app.py (Page 2)

9. student index follows the order the field is queried in app.py; 0 returns intern_id and index 1 returns full_name

Allocation page

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `127.0.0.1:5000/assigned_projects`. The page has a navigation bar with a 'View Archived' button, a 'Statuses' dropdown menu, and a 'Change Status' button. Below the navigation bar is a grid of 12 project cards, each with a status indicator (Status: 0 or Status: 1) and a 'Fields+' button. The projects are: Unassigned, BioNix, Clinical Dashboards, Clinical PDFs, Data Commons, Flux, Genomics Metadata Multiplexing, Haemosphere, Imaging, Immunology Web, Quantum Computing, and Research Data Workflows. Below the project cards is a grid of student cards. A student card for Samantha Lee (Sci) is highlighted in blue, and an arrow labeled '3' points to it, indicating a drag action. The student card for Samantha Lee (Sci) lists her fields: None, Translator, Genomics, Metadata, Multiplexing, and 03 Quick review.

1. page address `/assigned_projects`; determined in function in `app.py`
2. change the status (number of students assigned) of selected projects (checkbox)
3. dragging a student card will change the student's project from Clinical PDFs to Data Commons

Important – do not remove fields or change the order of SQL queries

Important Skills for Success – 10 minutes

1. Communication (MOST IMPORTANT)

- With teammates
- With supervisor
- Through documentation
- Clear, frequent updates, confirmation and clarifications

2. Soft Skills

- Continuous improvement mindset
- Tolerance for complexity
- Tolerance for ambiguity
- Critical thinking
- Adaptability
- Learnability
- Collaborative by default

3. Technical Skills

- Python
- SQL
- HTML/CSS

4. Process Understanding

Understand the processes you want to streamline and ensure your vision matches the supervisor's vision. Don't build features in isolation!

- **Don't build in isolation:** Always validate your understanding of the process with Rowland
- **Ask "why" questions:** Understand the reasoning behind current workflows before changing them
- **User-centered design:** Your solution should match the supervisor's actual needs, not just what seems logical

Common Pitfalls to Avoid

- Building features without understanding the full workflow
- Making UX changes without fixing underlying database issues
- Working individually without communicating with teammates
- Assuming you know what's needed without asking

What Previous Interns Got Right

- Have clear documentation
- Supporting each other while owning individual areas
- Ask Rowland questions to find out the main issues or required improvements. Then ask questions specific to or targeting that particular issue.
- Ask 'why?' Questions. Understanding 'why' things are designed in a particular way and how Rowland uses the app will allow you to work independently and more effectively later on.
- Before starting to code, run by your plans with Rowland
- Split tasks and plan out how to cut branches on GitHub

Summary of Changes Made 2025/2026 Summer

Refer to presentation slides and technical diaries for code and more details

Database Normalisation (10 minutes)

Previously, the student table stored status, intake, project, and pre-internship internal evaluation information as **TEXT** values (e.g., "14 Finished", "Summer 2024").

Solution:

Normalise database to use **foreign key IDs** pointing to lookup tables.

Steps taken:

1. Add new ID columns for status, intake, project and internal evaluation in Students table
2. Create new table Internal_eval_level to store pre-internship evaluation levels with its IDs
3. Populate new IDs
4. Update App.py and html code to use the new ID fields

Before	After
status	status_id
project	project_id
intake	intake_id
pre_internship_summary_recommendation_internal	pre_internship_internal_eval_level_id

SQL script to migrate the above changes:

```
cat sql_upgrades/normalisation_update.sql | sqlite3  
student_intern_data/student_intern_data.db
```

New functionality: add & edit feature for statuses and internal evaluation levels via UI (5 minutes)

Adding new status and pre-internship internal evaluation level or editing existing status/level name in database is possible only via SQL alteration

Solution:

1. Created index pages for status and pre-internship internal evaluation level with the same structure to projects and intakes

2. The respective index pages can be assessed through the newly added Status and Pre-internship internal evaluation buttons on the page header

Helpful Links – 10 minutes

Previous interns' (Intake 13) final presentations: [Final Presentation .url](#)

GitHub repository: [Forked GitHub repository](#)

Example individual learning plan: [ILP](#)

Individual learning plan folder: [Individual learning plan](#)

Team notes: [Student organiser notes.docx](#)

Past technical diary folder: [Technical diary](#)

Presentation slides: [intern presentation.pptx](#)

Whiteboard: [Canva whiteboard](#)

Learning materials that might be helpful:

[Flask tutorial](#) – YouTube playlist explains the fundamentals of flask and how it works backend.